

Research Article

Empirical validity of basic profile and conceptual evaluation model of the annual performance appraisal process of the National Colleges of Education lecturers in Sri Lanka

N. Kumara Pathiraja,

Lecturer (SLTES), Maharagama National College of Education, Sri Lanka

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Abstract:

This study conducted of the empirical validity of basic profile and conceptual evaluation model of the annual performance appraisal process of the National Colleges of Education lecturers; implemented with the main purpose of redesigning the annual performance evaluation system. It seeks to identify new trends in the job performance evaluation process, as well as to study its core profile and provide practical advice on integrating of each areas into the development of the evaluation system. Includes a review of the literature related to the Annual Performance Excellence of National college of Education Lecturers and their Continuing Development of Higher Teacher Education Occupational Intentions. According to (Francis, 2019) the formal implementation of a performance appraisal feedback system serves a lots of effective purposes in the relationship between managers and subordinates. As (Jency, 2013) points out, for the success of any job appraisal system requires improved evaluation methods and employees feedback effective

procedure. For this study, qualitative and quantitative Methods Integrated Mixed Study Methodology were adopted according to the mixed method research paradigm. Data and information were collected using four mixed equipment developed from each of the study techniques of the questionnaire, interview, observation, and document review. Combined mixed sampling methods were followed within the sample framework of this study according to Probability and non-Probability methods. 325 participants were invited to a sample that was mixed according to cluster, purposive, field, simple random, systematic sampling patterns, of which 260 actually participated in the study. The sample size of 260 represents the actual population and the target population. Its confidence level is 95%. The margin of error is 5%. In the analysis of the collected primary and secondary data and information, the structural equation modelling and theme analysis methods were followed according to Microsoft Excel and Microsoft Word operating systems 2016. That is, the results were generated according to an integrated mixed analysis procedure of qualitative and quantitative methods.

The study results were compared with previous research findings, and adaptation from traditional-past oriented performance evaluation methods to modern-future oriented assessment methods is of priority requirement. This study were discovered eleven basic profile areas that are specific to the annual performance appraisal system. The Strategic Multilateral Feedback Performance Evaluation Model (Raghunadhan & Sequeira, 2013); (George, 2016); (Patil & Dalvi, 2019) works exceptionally well to cover this study gap. To cover the study gap by the researcher; The Multipartite Feedback Performance Appraisal System (MFPAS) and the NCOE Lecturer Performance Measurement Scale were redesigned. It will greatly assist in ensuring the efficient, effective and transparent service of lecturers in National Colleges of Education. The findings of this study; Feedback on job performance, such as top managers, moderators, appraisers, appraisees, etc., is of particular importance to key stakeholders. This study requires future research into the validity of

each of the redesigned models and procedures, and the development of modern technology online software that can integrate and implement those procedures.

Key words: Job performance profile, Performance appraisal methods, Performance Evaluation Indicators, Ethics of performance appraisal, Key stakeholders in feedback. Performance feedback process.

1. Introduction: This report includes the findings of the study on the empirical validity of the conceptual framework and the basic profile of the annual performance appraisal process of the National College of Education lecturers in Sri Lanka. It has been shown by (Peleyeju & Ojebiyi, 2013) that higher education is driven by global competition and forces such as expectations of quality, struggle for survival, deployment of capital and funds by various organizations, rapidly changing technology, and high costs. The contribution of the performance evaluation system should be considered to meet those challenges and ensure overall quality management in higher education institutions. The study has shown that the proper implementation of the performance appraisal system can motivate employees for more meaningful job performance. In order to focus on the research area and the study problem, the introduction of the problem, the need of the study, the background of the problem, the importance of the study, the scope of the study and the main purpose of the study work are addressed. (Jalaliyoon & Taherdoost, 2012) Point out that in the last few decades, higher education institutions have increased in number and due to the international competition, it is important to improve their strategies. That is, by establishing an employee performance evaluation system in organizations as a human resource management strategy, it is possible to achieve the future goals that are currently being faced globally. Performance appraisal is an essential part of any ideal organization. It helps to identify, innovate and improve various areas required to achieve human resource development and organizational development objectives. It is

also the basis for identifying the opportunities that help employees' career development and for the manager to understand those needs.

Performance appraisal is an essential part of any ideal organization. It helps to identify, innovate and improve various areas required to achieve human resource development and organizational development objectives. It is also the basis for identifying the opportunities that help employees' career development and for the manager to understand those needs. (Masron, Ahmad, & Rahim, 2012) Identified that Key Performance Indicators (KPI) such as teaching, research, supervision, publication and consultation are critical factors that show significant positive results in justifying the performance of academic staff in higher education institutions. But, revealing that key performance indicators are another aspect that has been neglected in the performance evaluation of lecturers, they point out that if higher education institutional authorities do not plan to monitor this matter accurately, and it will face negative consequences. Also the report of the Committee on Drafting a New Education Act for General Education (National Committee, 2009) points out that performance evaluation and measurement can accurately understand organizational impact. (Karunanayake, 2016) Presented proposals to the Parliament of Sri Lanka on the efficiency of the public service, the introduction of a performance evaluation system and a performance-based salary system through the budget proposals for the year 2017.

“... අප දන්නා පරිදි කළමනාකරණයේ දී භාවිත වන ප්‍රධාන කාර්ය සාධන දර්ශක (Key performance Indicators - KPIs) බොහෝ රටවල් විසින් සුබවාදී ව නම ආයතන හා සේවකයන්ගේ කාර්යසාධනය ඇගයීම සඳහා යොදා ගන්නවා. ඒ අනුව අවම වශයෙන් රාජ්‍ය අංශයේ ප්‍රමුඛ ආයතන කිහිපයකට වත් ප්‍රධාන කාර්ය සාධන දර්ශක හඳුන්වා දීමට ඇති හැකියාව අප විසින් සොයා බලනු ලබනවා.” (කරුණානායක, 2016 පි. 6, 7)

“... As we know, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) used in management are used by many countries to positively evaluate the performance of their organizations and employees. Accordingly, we are looking into the possibility of introducing key performance indicators to at least some of the leading institutions in the public sector.” (Karunanayake, 2016 p. 6, 7)

(Francis, 2019) Reveals that it is a standard practice in almost all organizations to evaluate the performance of relevant employees by the work supervisor in comparison with the past. Although the situation indicated a very important nature of human resource management, he found that it operated as a system that wasted work time and caused dissatisfaction among employees. It has been emphasized by (Robbins & Judge, 2013) that past service-oriented methods of performance appraisal, which included less hierarchies, need to change developmentally to suit modern organizational systems. Therefore, the main objective of this study was to identify the basic profile of the annual performance evaluation process of National College of Education lecturers and the empirical validity of the conceptual evaluation model. The strengths and weaknesses of the evaluation system as well as the evaluation methods used, measurement instruments, evaluation achievement levels, measurement codes and evaluation scales were studied. Based on those findings, the annual performance evaluation system of the National College of Education academic staff in Sri Lanka has been redesigned.

2. Definitions:

2.1 National Colleges of Education (NCOE); Although teaching is recognized as a qualification according to the National Educational Institutions (NIE) Act No. 28 of 1985 (Parliament of Sri Lanka, 1985), the teacher education institutions established for the purpose of conducting educational courses which can award degree diplomas and other Academic excellence in the institution are called National Colleges of Education. That is, NCOE means the nineteen National Colleges of Education of Sri Lanka established under the provisions of the Colleges of Education Act No. 30 of 1986 (Parliament of Sri Lanka, 1986).

2.2 NCOE Lecturers; NCOE Lecturers means all grade I II, III staff officers working in the 19 National Colleges of Education, governed under the Sri Lanka Teacher Educator Service

Regulations dated 11.03.1999 No. 1070/13 (PSC of Sri Lanka, 1999) and 28.07.2015 No. 1925/37 (PSC of Sri Lanka, 2015).

2.3 Lecturer Performance; Lecturer performance refers to the active behaviour of the tasks, contextual and adaptive (Pradhan & Jena, 2017) tasks practically performed by the National College of Education lecturers in their professional role to achieve organizational goals. That is, to further develop positive behaviours, as well as through the feedback process of transforming negative behaviours into positive behaviours in an appropriate manner, is the expected organizational value (Motowidlo & Kell, 2012) from each lecturer.

2.4 Annual performance appraisal process; the annual performance appraisal process refers to the systematic and structured (Aggarwal & Thakur, 2013) institutional continuous functionality of the appraisal system, which includes multilateral feedback to evaluate the actual performance of the National College of Education lecturers annually. According to Study findings (Pathiraja N. K., 2022) the annual performance evaluation process of the National Colleges of Education consists of six areas of step opportunity. Namely, 1. Professional Competency Analysis 2. Planning, organizing and directing annual activities 3. Performance-based professional practice 4. Career guidance, support, feedback 5. Performance appraisal every four months 6. Review and professional development based on evaluation results.

2.5 NCOE Lecturer Performance Profile; The NCOE Lecturer Performance Profile is a user-friendly job analysis (Chaser, 2018) human resource management tool (AltaFlux Corporation, 2017) that includes accurate predictive information (Heathfield, 2019) about each lecturer's professional performance. An NCOE Lecturer Performance Profile includes information (Rouse, 2009) on personal qualities, values, professional skills, job responsibilities, work experience, educational credentials, behavioural notes, performance levels, work environment conditions, financial incentives, salary range, job mobility and feedback, etc.

3. Objectives of the research: The main objective of this study was to explore the current system of annual performance appraisal of NCOE lecturers in Sri Lanka and to redesign an effective appraisal system according to modern management principles. Under that first; to identify the existing performance appraisal process for evaluating NCOE lecturers in Sri Lanka. Secondly; Analysing the strengths and weaknesses of the measurement instruments used to evaluate lecturer performance. Thirdly; to investigate the need for a new performance evaluation system that can accurately represent the performance level of National College of Education teachers and finally; Redesigning a more effective evaluation system that accurately reflects the performance level of NCOE lecturers. That is, based on these four basic objectives, the study process was planned and launched. According to the findings of that study a NCOE lecturer performance evaluation system is presented in accordance with modern human resource management concepts to identify efficient educators who can be respected among heterogeneous groups of employees, which will act as a way to obtain better and more prestigious service.

4. Literature review: The research literature found locally on the annual performance appraisal process of NCOE lecturers in Sri Lanka was insufficient to build the theoretical foundation of this study. Empirical studies conducted on performance appraisal systems related to other staff services, similar to the service of NCOE lecturers, were therefore relied upon. Sufficient research literature was found in countries such as Sri Lanka, India, Japan, China, United Kingdom, USA and Australia. That is, an attempt has been made to identify the theoretical basis and study gap related to this study based on the empirical research literature on the performance evaluation systems of local and foreign higher education institutions, teacher education institutions, and universities. Under that, theoretical concepts related to the annual performance evaluation process such as basic profile of employee performance evaluation system, job performance, performance management, performance evaluation methods, annual performance evaluation process, evaluation ethics and performance

evaluation indicators were investigated. A framework for management by objectives (MBO) was proposed in the study (Robbins & Judge, 2013) of a useful approach to promote the realignment of organizational and individual priorities to manage performance. This research discusses the objectives of performance appraisal and explores different approaches to appraisal schemes, their advantages and disadvantages. Performance improvement strategies such as mentoring that can build collaboration and partnership between experienced and less experienced individuals with the aim of providing support, guidance and feedback to professional development as a resource in performance appraisal systems have been explored.

In particular, (Mullegamgoda, 2016) points out that performance appraisal and management has a history since 1800 AD and it has been adopted since 1990 AD to evaluate employee performance in the IT industry. But as (KPI Institute, 2019) points out, in the 1970s in America and from the 1980s to the 1990s in Britain, state legislation was enacted regarding equal rights and civil rights. Accordingly, the organizations started to adopt some kind of method for evaluating the tasks of the employees. Performance Management Systems (PMS) were used in the 1980's and 1990's as effective tools for trying to change the work culture and ethos in the public sector. As disclosed by (Brudan, 2010) traditionally, performance management in the organizational context has three levels. That is, the three levels of performance management are strategic, operational and individual. As the main objective of the researcher is based on individual performance evaluation, special attention is given to it. The extent of an employee's performance in an organizational context is the individual level (Pathiraja N. K., 2022). Although implemented at the individual level, performance management consists of an integrated and planned system to continuously improve the performance of all employees. The (KPI Institute, 2019) points out that the performance management system includes the tasks of defining work goals and standards, reviewing performance in accordance with

those standards, managing performance at all levels of operation, and maximizing learning and development.

4.1 Basic profile of the annual performance appraisal process: Employee performance is a central variable in employment relationships, but until recently, profile of appraisal have received little attention. As indicated by (Ismail & Sherwani, 2018) employee performance is considered as a multi-faceted dimension of every aspect of a job. That is, task performance, contextual performance, job reduction, decisions etc. are the profile areas. Performance can be simply defined as the employee's ability to meet the responsibilities as outlined in the job description. The (Igbojekwe, 2015) study identified three categories of academic staff evaluation profile areas namely teaching, research and service. He has suggested that teaching effectiveness should be evaluated based on students' criticism. Also, a number of problems and grading errors were found related to the subjectivity found in a performance appraisal profile. Those problems and errors can be classified as effects for personal gain, opposition, moderate tendency, strict evaluation, light grading, novice behaviour, over-influence, initial impressions and criticism etc.

As revealed by (Mullegamgoda, 2016), there are 09 attributes that lead to superior results in a performance appraisal profile. Accordingly, an evaluation profile should include the attributes of system satisfaction, motivation, job satisfaction, goal setting, self-evaluation, evaluation interviews, employee participation, personal development, and pay for performance. He also points out that a performance appraisal profile should cover the main qualities of fairness and impartiality, employee participation in the process, clearly defined objectives, employee recognition, feedback quantity and quality, self-evaluation and evaluation of the employee's job relevance. With the aim of broadening the scope of employee performance (Pradhan & Jena, 2017) based on feedback, a conceptual framework for empirical validation and a 38-item instrument on employee performance dimensions were developed. This performance appraisal tool includes three main profile areas. That is, the items

included in the three performance profile areas of task, adaptation and contextual are 12, 12 and 14 respectively. But (Mushi., 2016) identified three types of errors in a performance profile as human errors, central tendency errors, and general errors. It also reveals many measures to be followed to overcome these problems. Common errors in a performance profile can be overcome by adopting measures such as use of multiple criteria, emphasis on behaviour, and use of multiple raters, selective assessment, training of raters, and training on performance standards, feedback, group discussion training and behavioural documentation. Also (Palupi, Cahjono, & Dananti, 2018) study has addressed the development of software that includes prototyping of integrated assessment model. This study revealed that a performance evaluation profile of lecturers includes the four areas of academic Proficiency, social Proficiency, professional Proficiency and personal Proficiency.

4.2 Job performance: As indicated by (Robertson & Cooper, 2015) job performance is the good ranking with organizational assumptions about the requirements of a professional role. According to (Ismail & Sherwani, 2018) there are two types of job performance. That is, task performance and contextual performance. Task performance is defined as the cognitive ability to perform specific tasks assigned in relation to the job role. Its performance depends on individual personality, and this is a practical situation of accepted behavioral tasks or behavioral roles based on job descriptions. Contextual performance refers to value-based and additional behavioral roles that are not covered by job descriptions and job compensation, and are additional roles that are indirectly related to organizational performance. But (Bennett, Lance, & Woehr, 2014) point out that contextual performance is the set of contributions based on individual performance balanced social behavior that supports organizational culture. That is, context-based performance has a similar relationship with citizenship performance. As (Martin, 2011) points out, job performance is interpreted in terms of pay systems, awards and salary-based grade systems that are directly related to organizational performance. But (Pradhan & Jena, 2017) revealed three main factors that represent new dimensions

of job performance. That is, in addition to the above-mentioned task performance and contextual performance, another aspect called adaptive performance was found. As (CultureIQ, 2019) points out, job performance is the assessment of whether an employee has performed his job well. Individual evaluation is one based on the effort of one individual. The HR department usually manages the evaluation of job functions. But performance appraisal is a very important process for the overall success of the organization. Individual performance is a very important basis for that. According to (Motowidlo & Kell, 2012) study findings, job performance is the overall value expected by the organization about the different types of behavior structures that each employee performs in a standard period of time. That is, job performance is an attribute of employee behavior. It is a composite attribute of various types of variable behavior that occurs over a specific period of time. Employee behaviors that can make a difference in achieving organizational goals can be classified as positive behaviors, and employee behaviors that hinder the achievement of organizational goals can be classified as negative behaviors. Accordingly, the expected organizational value from each employee can be simply defined as job performance. Also, (Maheesha & Perera, 2018) found that incentive programs have a positive effect on job performance. Corporate incentives with positive effects are of two types, financial and non-financial. Implementation of incentive programs, both financial and non-financial, was found essential to improve job performance. But, (Sembiring & Ferine, 2018) study found that human resource development and consequently job satisfaction affects employee performance. They show that the human resource development of an organization significantly affects job performance, and that employee satisfaction resulting from the organizational human resource development has a significant effect on job performance in a unique way.

4.3 Performance Appraisal Methods: According to the findings presented by the study of Performance Appraisal: Methods and Rating Errors (Lunenburg, 2012), performance appraisal is the

systematic observing and evaluation of employees' performance. A classification of performance evaluation methods was presented under three evaluation approaches, the judgmental approach, the absolute standards approach, and the results oriented approach. He reveals that although performance appraisal should be completely accurate and objective based, the evaluation process is not accurate and objective based, resulting in rating errors. Among those rating errors, it was specifically identified that there are errors of severity or lightness, moderate tendency, influence of personal relationships and repetition of events. But (Jency, 2013) points out that performance appraisal methods can be classified based on the type of organization, size and time period used. Also (Aggarwal & Thakur, 2013) has pointed out that there are many techniques used for performance evaluation. What technical system should be used to evaluate the performance of employees? Clarifies that it depends on the type and size of the organization. The results of the study revealed that it is very difficult to say that one technology is better than another, and that each technology has its advantages and disadvantages.

According to (Pawar, 2016), a performance appraisal method is a systematic and Timeless process that assesses an individual employee's job performance and Productivity relative to pre-established criteria and organizational objectives. Similar to the definition identified by Pawar, (Roychoudhuri, 2018) points out that a performance appraisal method is a systematic process that evaluates the performance of an individual employee in terms of his productivity relative to a set of predetermined objectives. It includes annual activities and feedback. It also evaluates the employee's attitude, personality, behavior and consistency in his job profile. Appraisal has various applications in compensation, performance improvement, promotion, termination, test validation and many more. Each organization adopts different types of performance appraisal methods. He points out that evaluations facilitate communication between management and employees, and act as a means of understanding the expectations of management of the organization to employees. Thus, it is clear

that the criteria for performance evaluation methods are based on various aspects such as the effectiveness, quality, service time and training of the employees.

According to (Pathiraja N. K., 2022), (Aggarwal & Thakur, 2013) and (Jency, 2013) employee performance evaluation methods can be classified as traditional methods and modern methods. According to their studies, they show that traditional methods are old methods of performance evaluation and modern methods were developed to improve those traditional methods. Traditional methods are based on studying the personal qualities of employees, which include job knowledge, initiative, loyalty, leadership, and judgment. But Agarwal and Thakur also revealed that modern methods have tried to improve the shortcomings of old methods such as bias, impersonality, etc. According to (HRM, 2012), formal methods of systematic evaluation of an individual's job performance and potential for development can be called performance evaluation methods. It is a causal finding for the study of work-related behaviors and outcomes. It is an efficient, structured costing system, as is performance and how tasks are performed efficiently in the future. It involves evaluating work-related behaviors and outcomes, finding reasons for performance, and how to work effectively and efficiently in the future, benefiting the employee, the organization, and society. According to (Shaout & Yousif, 2014); (Hoque, 2015); (Montather, 2014); (HRM, 2012); (Mullegamgoda, 2016) and (Pathiraja N. K., 2022) studies, performance evaluation methods can be broadly classified as past oriented methods and future oriented methods.

5. Research method and process: This study was mainly oriented as a research of mixed method research approach. For that, (Kamble, 2017), (Johnson, 2017), (Khahan, Chaiprasit, & Pukkeeree, 2017) etc. were based on the theoretical facts about adopting the mixed method approach. According to (Patterson, 2013), (Bainbridge & Lee, 2014), (Peersman, 2014) and (Olivier, 2017), the components of mixed study instruments, mixed methodology philosophical background, theoretical framework, rationale for using mixed methodology, instrument development, mixing strategies,

sampling, using qualitative and quantitative mixed analysis methods etc. were discussed. Arguments were presented about the use of 04 data collection techniques, which are document analysis method, semi-structured questionnaire method, interview method and observation method, and the development of those instruments according to mixed techniques. All aspects and practical considerations such as sampling, measurement scales, reliability and validity and data analysis procedures were carried out to justify the study data. The use of qualitative and quantitative mixed analysis methods was discussed under data analysis methods. According to Microsoft Excel 2016 and Microsoft Word 2016 operating systems, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used to analyze quantitative data and information. While analyzing the qualitative data, thematic analysis steps such as coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes were followed. Qualitative data and informational thematic analysis results were reported using patterns, codes, categories, core categories. That is a mixed analysis procedure was followed to examine the primary and secondary data sets generated by the mixed study of quantitative and qualitative methods.

6. Analysis of data and information:

The data and information of this study will be analyzed and the results and overall findings will be presented. The main objective was to provide answers to the research questions as well as to examine quantitatively and qualitatively under the mixed methods approach with the study objectives. To achieve the study objectives, the data were analyzed using a combination of all three forms of data namely qualitative study data, pilot study data and quantitative study data. Data exploration and descriptive analysis of the phenomena to be explored in the form of document review, observations and interview questions related to key themes were included. That is, for the efficiency and effectiveness of the current performance evaluation system, it covers the basic information of employee performance, the concept of employee performance, performance evaluation process,

performance management, lecturer performance evaluation, as well as the basic information of job performance.

A mixed methodology was adopted in aligning the findings related to the collected data and information according to the research objectives and research questions. By using the study methods of open and semi-structured interviews, structured and unstructured participant observation, as well as survey questionnaires and document reviews, it was possible to collect sufficient data and information about the study problem and the validity of the conceptual evaluation model. Procedures of data and information analysis began after examining the collected data. That is, checking for missing data, identifying additional data, testing for normality of classification and grouping data sets, and testing for homogeneity and mixed multilinearity. The final stage consisted of uncovering the relationship between the objectives of the study and the phenomena. That is to identify the hidden phenomena in the annual performance evaluation process of National College of Education lecturers. Therefore, the findings were confirmed after a step-by-step assessment of the structural model of the research and the analytical results of the study data and information. In structural modeling, the researcher followed the steps of identifying, evaluating, testing, and modifying model specifications, with the best fit model confirming findings based on answers to research questions and results.

7. Conclusions: The main objectives of the study were to examine the relevance of the study findings, results and findings to the underlying questions and arguments. Accordingly, recommendations were made through conclusions and suggestions about the empirical validity of the integrated evaluation model used to evaluate the performance of lecturers at the National College of Education. Eleven key profile areas were identified in this study. That is, Rules of Procedure, performance objectives, performance management, performance stakeholders, job functions, professional identity, corporate identity, performing tasks, Performance Assurance, Performance judgments and performance benefits. Based on those findings and the primary objective of the

research, the general model used to evaluate the performance of National College of Education lecturers was redesigned.

It was revealed that the annual performance appraisal process of National College of Education lecturers does not operate according to the principles of performance appraisal and is merely maintained as a document file based on annual certification of lecturers' service and payment of annual salary increments. It was revealed that the performance evaluation model currently used to evaluate lecturers does not include eight elements of human resource management and job performance in the annual evaluation process. That is, 1. Non-integration of elements of job evaluation, 2. Not determining the level of evaluation according to the measurement scale, 3. Non-conduct of performance review, 4. Not considering the previous year's evaluation results, 5. Not being a performance based evaluation system, 6. Using a common staff appraisal model, 7. Operating as a personal relationship based assessment method, 8. Not being a multilateral and multi-source evaluation system. In the annual performance evaluation of the National College of Education lecturers, it was revealed that the actual performance level earned by each lecturer in performing their duties is not assessed, and therefore the actual performance of the lecturers is not represented in the assessment results. Also, it was revealed that the National College of Education in Sri Lanka does not follow a formal evaluation system to evaluate the annual performance of the lecturers, which has naturally created a number of problems. That is, it was revealed that the current system for evaluating the annual performance of National College of Education lecturers in Sri Lanka contains the basic characteristics found in the traditional evaluation methods that are oriented towards the past.

8. Recommendations and suggestions: Each lecturer should be assigned duties after a professional competency analysis. It is also suggested that each lecturer's academic proficiency, professional proficiency level, job attractiveness, self-commitment, work experience, job productivity, and

professional development should be based on the factors of professional skills analysis. Annual performance appraisal system should be implemented in accordance with job description, setting performance standards, evaluation scales, indicators and criteria. Performance evaluation should be based on multiple HR sources in terms of reviews including internal and external parties such as students, peers, and self-assessment. To that end, based on the findings of this study, the Multilateral Feedback Performance Appraisal System (MFPAS) presented by Section 8.2 (p. 15) is proposed. In the annual performance evaluation, the performance level should be assessed according to the evaluation scale of very excellent, excellent, very good, good, Satisfactory, weak and Very weak, based on criteria-based points. To that end, based on the findings of this study, the NCOE Lecturer Performance Appraisal Scale model presented by Section 8.3 (p. 16) is proposed. It is suggested that the performance indicators should be composed according to the four job skills namely technical, social, professional and personal, and the performance evaluation should be done according to the three main activities of education, research and community service.

8.1 Directions for future research: In this research, the Empirical validity of basic profile and conceptual evaluation model of the annual performance appraisal process of the National Colleges of Education lecturers in Sri Lanka were studied. Under this, Future research is needed on the validity of each of the proposed models and procedures, as well as the development of modern technology online software that can implement these procedures and models in combination.

8.2 Model: Multilateral Feedback Performance Appraisal System (MFPAS)

For lecturers of the National College of Education in Sri Lanka

Source: Study Analytical Findings and Disclosure (Pathiraja N. K., 2022)

8.3 Model: NCOE Lecturer Performance Appraisal Scale

The percentage gap in terms of employment capacity	Job Performance Quality Level (JPQL)	Performance Review Score Range (PRSR)	Annual Performance Benefits (APB)
Points units 100 99 98 97 96 95 94 93 92 91 90 89 88 87 86 85 84 83 82 81 80 79 78 77 76 75 74 73 72 71 70 69 68 67 66 65 64 63 62 61 60 59 58 57 56 55 54 53 52 51 50 49 48 47 46 45 44 43 42 41 40 39 38 37 36 35 34 33 32 31 30 29 28 27 26 25 24 23 22 21 20 19 18 17 16 15 14 13 12 11 10 09 08 07 06 05 04 03 02 01	A → Very excellent level	KPI - Level I 90 - 100 points	Awarding three additional points for grade promotion and three additional salary increments
	B → Excellent level	KPI - Level II 80 - 89 points	Grant of two additional points for grade promotion and two additional salary increments
	C → Very good level	KPI - Level III 70 - 79 points	Grant of one additional mark for grade promotion and one additional salary increment
	D → Good level	KPI - Level IV 60 - 69 points	Payment of annual salary increment, appreciation of service and issuance of commendation certificate for grade promotions
	E → Satisfactory level	KPI - Level V 50 - 59 points	Payment of annual salary increment and recognition for grade promotion
	F → Average level	KPI - Level VI 40 - 49 points	Temporarily suspending salary increments and recommending performance feedback for grade promotion
	G → Weak level	KPI - Level VII 30 - 39 points	Reducing salary increment, withholding grade promotion and prescribing performance feedback
	H → Very weak level	KPI - Level VIII 01 - 29 points	Permanent stoppage of salary increment in the relevant year (In a non-refundable manner), Recommendation that performance is ineffective and refer to special professional development programs

Source: Study Analytical Findings and Disclosure (Pathiraja N. K., 2022)

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